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Research Article

**TO DETERMINE THE PREVALENCE OF CIRRHOTIC
CARDIOMYOPATHY IN PATIENTS OF LIVER CIRRHOSIS*****Dr. Muhammad Zeeshan Riaz, **Dr. Rana Mohammad Yasir Bari, **Dr. Zain Fatima**

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Abstract**Objective:** To evaluate the prevalence of cirrhosis cardiomyopathy in patients with liver cirrhosis.**Study design:** A cross-sectional research (descriptive).**Place and Duration:** In the Medicine Department, Unit I of Allied Hospital, Faisalabad in collaboration with Cardiology Department for one year duration from June 2017 to June 2018.**Methods:** 300 total patients were included in this analysis. The presence of diastolic dysfunction in patients with liver cirrhosis (eg, long-term ratio with operational definition E / A or delay time increase) was ruled out by a consultant cardiology echocardiography diagnosed as cirrhosis cardiomyopathy.**Results:** Of the 37 patients (12.3%) who were between 20 and 30 years of age, 148 (49.4%) were between 41 and 50 years. The mean age was 46.7 ± 8.9 years. 127 (42.3%) of the patients were female, while the gender distribution was 173 (57.7%). Child-Pugh classification was as follows: 38 patients (12.7%) belonged to Child-Pugh A, 118 patients (39.3%) to Child-Pugh B, and 144 patients (48.0%) belonged to Child-Pugh C. cirrhotic cardiomyopathy Ser 147 (49.0%). Stratification The child was made for the stage of the disease according to the Pugh class.**Conclusion:** This analysis shows that cirrhotic cardiomyopathy is a common event. While there is a direct association between the severity of liver disease and cirrhotic cardiomyopathy, electrophysiological, biochemical and echocardiographic changes are the basis of the situation.**Key Words:** cirrhotic cardiomyopathy, liver cirrhosis, echocardiography.**Corresponding author:****Dr. Muhammad Zeeshan Riaz,**
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INTRODUCTION:

Cirrhosis is a very common disease in Pakistan. Necrosis of liver cells, it follows the formation of fibrosis and nodules. It has several important complications. One of them is cirrhotic cardiomyopathy and its prevalence is 50%. Cardiomyopathy is a group of myocardial diseases affecting the mechanical or electrical function of the heart. Cirrhotic cardiomyopathy is a newly diagnosed pathology in the liver cirrhosis, which occurs in the absence of other associated heart diseases. In general, it is silent or clinically mild, but stresses may increase excessive heart failure such as in transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt insertion or liver transplantation. In the hepatorenal syndrome pathogenesis stress is a stimulator. In the natural history of cirrhosis, it is largely accepted as a potential cause of mortality and morbidity. Diagnosis can be made if systolic or diastolic dysfunction (confirmed by echocardiography) is accompanied by support criteria such as abnormal serum markers or electrophysiological abnormalities. There is still no definitive diagnostic criteria. Treatment of cirrhotic cardiomyopathy is insufficient. Beta-blockers can be administered in patients with long QT interval because Henriksen et al. Report that acute administration of single-dose propranolol in cirrhotic patients improves the prolonged QT interval. Long-term antagonism of aldosterone may be useful in preventing myocardial hypertrophy. Vasodilators such as ACE inhibitors not be given because of the chances of further exacerbation of the systemic vasodilator condition. After heart failure develops, measures such as bed rest, salt and water restriction, diuretic treatment and careful reduction of the preliminary load with appropriate drugs should be considered. Cirrhotic cardiomyopathy has not yet been diagnosed and is not treated in particular in developing countries such as Pakistan, because this condition is not known and there are no specific diagnostic criteria. The reason for my analysis is to evaluate the prevalence of cirrhotic cardiomyopathy

in liver cirrhosis patients and to increase awareness of the present disease..

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional research (descriptive).was held in the Medicine Department, Unit I of Allied Hospital, Faisalabad in collaboration with Cardiology Department for one year duration from June 2017 to June 2018. Sample volume of 300 cases is calculated by a confidence level of 95%, 6% error and an expected percentage edge of cirrhosis cardiomyopathy, ie 50% in patients with liver cirrhosis. Sampling technique is non probability sampling. Patients were enrolled in both sexes between 20 and 60 years of age with liver cirrhosis. These previous clinical histories of congenital heart disease, previous clinical history and previous clinical history were excluded from study patients with ischemic heart disease in vulvular heart disease. After the written informed consent, a total of 300 cases were chosen which met the inclusion criteria. Your information was collected through a form. Demographic information was included in the name, age and gender. The Child-pugh class was calculated for all patients (added as Annex B). After informed consent, patients were referred to the cardiology unit for echocardiography by a single consultant cardiologist. Diagnosis of cirrhotic cardiomyopathy in liver cirrhosis patients increasing the rate of diastolic dysfunction (for example, increasing rate D / A or a prolonged slowdown as a defined procedure). compiled and analyzed using the 17.0 version of SPSS. Mean and standard deviation for age and quantitative variables were calculated. The presence of gender, cirrhotic cardiomyopathy and cirrhosis stage are presented as frequency and percentage as qualitative variables. By Child Pugh class (A, B, C).

RESULTS:

300 total patients were included in this analysis. The majority of the patients were between the ages of 41-50 and 148 (49.4%) were between the ages of 20-30. The mean age was 46.7 ± 8.9 years (Table 1).

Table 1: Distribution of patients by age (n=300)

Age in years	=n	%age
20-30	37	12.3
31-40	49	16.3
41-50	148	49.4
51-60	66	22.0

Mean±SD: 46.7±8.9

In the distribution by gender, 173 patients (57.7%) were male and 127 (42.3%) were female (Table-2).

Table 2: Distribution of patients by sex (n=300)

Gender	=n	%age
Male	173	57.7
Female	127	42.3

The Child-Pugh classification was as follows: 38 patients (12.7%) belonged to Child-Pugh A, 118 patients (39.3%) belonged to Child-Pugh B, and 144 patients (48.0%) belonged to Child-Pugh C (Table. 3).

Table 3: Distribution of patients by Child-Pugh classification (n=300)

Child Pugh classification	=n	%age
A	38	12.7
B	118	39.3
C	144	48.0

Cirrhotic cardiomyopathy was 147 (49.0%) (Table-4).

Table 4: Distribution of patients by cirrhotic cardiomyopathy (n=300)

Cirrhotic cardiomyopathy	=n	%age
Yes	147	49.0
No	153	51.0

Table 5 shows the stratification for the stage of the disease according to the Child Pugh class.

Table 5: Stratification for stage of disease by Child Pugh Class (n=147)

Child classification	Pugh	Cirrhotic cardiomyopathy	
		=n	%age
A		18	12.2
B		56	38.1
C		73	49.7

DISCUSSION:

Cirrhosis cardiomyopathy is a pathological condition defined as "chronic heart disorder in patients with cirrhosis characterized by sudden stress response and / or impaired diastolic relaxation with electrophysiological abnormalities in the absence of known cardiac disease". Cirrhosis of the liver is associated with various cardiovascular disorders. Patients with liver cirrhosis have normal resting systolic function. As cirrhosis progresses, a hyperdynamic circulation occurs, characterized by a high ejection fraction, increased cardiac output and tachycardia. This systolic dysfunction is masked when the patient is exposed to physical or pharmacological stress. In bacterial infections such as spontaneous bacterial peritonitis requiring high cardiac output, systolic insufficiency is evident. Open heart failure is usually a feature of cirrhotic cardiomyopathy because the accompanying vasodilation associated with the hyperdynamic circulation significantly reduces post-ventricular load. Evidence of a lack of adequate cardiac output

was further strengthened when hepatorenal syndrome developed as a result of low cardiac output. Cardiac systolic function is suppressed by negative inotropic cytokines such as TNF and interleukin-1b produced by an infection leading to the development of hepatorenal syndrome. In this study, the presence of cirrhotic cardiomyopathy appears to be up to 25% to 51% increase in children with cirrhosis cardiomyopathy frequency class B directly related to the severity of the disease associated with echocardiographic changes. In this study, comparable to the study performed by Shaikh et al., Who showed 44.6% of cirrhosis cardiomyopathy. Into two types Echocardiographic abnormalities of these patients were classified: diastolic dysfunction and systolic dysfunction]. Doppler ultrasound technique was used in this study to evaluate these anomalies (transthoracic approach) with color flow. Systolic dysfunction was considered to be present when the ejection fraction was > 55% at rest. While other studies such as Classical, Baik and colleagues have focused on resting echo abnormalities in this study,

stressful environments during echocardiography were focused on. The plus of my study is that the study is simple in an invasive technique (ECHO), which can be widely used in cardiology units used in design. The results are comparable to other similar studies. Identification of cirrhotic cardiomyopathy at an early stage and treatment can reduce the morbidity and mortality of cirrhotic patients and improve the quality of life.

CONCLUSION:

This study shows that cirrhotic cardiomyopathy is a common event. While electrophysiological changes constitute a basis for echocardiographic and biochemical status, there is a direct association between severity of liver disease and cirrhotic cardiomyopathy.

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